

LIMNOLOGY AROUND (A MORE EXTREME) WORLD: USA

Climate Change, Snow Droughts, and Shifting Stream Ecosystems in the Mountains

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Climate change is transforming the seasonal rhythms of rivers and lakes in mountain ranges across the globe. Snowpacks are thinning, snowmelt is occurring earlier, and streams that once flowed cold and fast well into summer now regularly enter prolonged low-flow periods. Snow droughts, or years with unusually low snowpacks and accelerated melting, are emerging as a central expression of climate warming. In the western United States, snow droughts have become longer and more intense over the last four decades, and the region has been identified as a global hotspot for changing snow dynamics (Huning and AghaKouchak 2020; Siirila-Woodburn *et al.* 2021). These hydrologic changes are a challenge for water managers and are reshaping freshwater ecosystems (Power *et al.* 2024). However, these ecological changes are difficult to predict.

In my research group at the University of California, Berkeley, we have been examining how snow droughts alter the rates and timing of key ecological processes and what this means for the linkages between aquatic and terrestrial environments. We are approaching these questions via a combination of long-term observations and large-scale field experiments in California's Sierra Nevada (e.g., Leathers *et al.* 2024; Cowell *et al.* 2025; Evangelista *et al.* 2025; Leathers *et al.* 2025), with the goal of combining attention to mechanisms with ecological realism.

Global analyses provide a sense of the scale of current and impending hydrologic shifts. Using a standardized Snow Water Equivalent Index derived from NASA's Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications (MERRA-2), Huning and AghaKouchak (2020) showed that in the western United States, snow droughts between 1980 and 2018 became more prevalent, more intense, and approximately 28% longer. At the same time, observational work has documented significant declines in mountain snowpack across the region. Mote *et al.* (2018) reported that April snowpack had decreased at more than 90% of long-term monitoring sites in the western U.S. (33% of which significantly), with losses in the order of 15-30% in average end-of-winter snow water equivalent relative to the past mid-century conditions. In California's Sierra Nevada, high-resolution modelling suggests that the midpoint of annual runoff could occur roughly 25 days earlier under a mitigated emissions scenario and approximately 50 days earlier under a business-as-usual scenario by the end of the century (Reich *et al.* 2018).

Earlier snowmelt, reduced snow-water storage, and warmer air temperatures combine to produce longer and hotter summers with extended periods of low-to-no flow. However, quantifying and predicting ecological responses to these hydrological shifts remains difficult for three major reasons. First, there is a challenge in accurately capturing the cross-scale interactions between regional climate and local hydrology. Even when climate change is the main driver of long-term shifts in hydrology (e.g., in driving shifts from perennial to intermittent flow regimes; Carlson *et al.* 2024), ecological responses are filtered through local-scale variation, from groundwater inputs and channel geomorphology to riparian shading. As a result, communities may show strong spatial variation in how they respond to the same climate stress. Second, due to the difficulty to capture,

via experiments or monitoring, the wide range of processes that are relevant to food-web dynamics and occur at different timescales. Stream organisms can respond to climate change via a wide range of mechanisms, such as physiological, behavioral (including changes in feeding preferences), and phenological; however, most past studies have typically focused on changes in population or community structure. As Kharouba and Wolkovich (2020) argue, there are persistent disconnects between theory and data in the study of phenological mismatches. Last but not least, stream ecosystems do not occur in a vacuum, but rather they are connected to the terrestrial environment via fluxes of organisms and nutrients (Baxter *et al.* 2005). While we know that emerging stream insects transfer critical nutrients (e.g., long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids) to riparian predators such as spiders, birds, and bats; it remains largely unstudied how drought could alter the strength, timing, and quality of these cross-ecosystem linkages.

Given these complexities, my group has used experimental approaches to probe the potential mechanisms by which climate-induced changes in snowmelt and low flows affect stream communities and food webs. In an experiment at the Sierra Nevada Aquatic Research Laboratory (see the experimental setting in the front page), we manipulated the timing and duration of low-flow periods under otherwise realistic environmental conditions (Leathers *et al.* 2024). We implemented three flow regimes: a "current" hydrograph mimicking present-day snowmelt timing, and two "future" regimes in which the onset of summer low flow was advanced by three and six weeks, respectively (Fig. 1). These offsets were selected based on projections of Sierra Nevada runoff timing under different greenhouse gas scenarios (Reich *et al.* 2018). We then monitored epilithic biofilm metabolism (gross primary production and ecosystem respiration), benthic

Fig. 1 (Above) Network of artificial stream channels at the Sierra Nevada Aquatic Research Lab (Mammoth Lakes, California), used to mimic the behavior of headwater streams under present-day conditions and future climate change scenarios. Credit: Albert Ruhí. (Below) Historical and future flow regimes of Convict Creek, an illustrative example of a Sierra Nevada headwater stream vulnerable to ongoing and future climate change. The green dashed lines indicate seasonal trends in the mean daily discharge from March to November each year from 1960 to 1974, as measured by a nearby USGS gaging station. The black line represents the daily mean discharge, and the orange dotted line illustrates the projected peak runoff and low-flow conditions advancing up to 6 weeks, in agreement with the downscaled climate change projections from Reich *et al.* 2018. Credit: Kyle Leathers.

invertebrate dynamics, and emergent insects at a high temporal resolution across the spring-summer growing season. Earlier and extended low flows intensified mid-season ecosystem respiration. This result suggests that ecosystem processes may show strong intra-seasonal sensitivity to flow timing. Invertebrate communities also showed fine-scale phenological shifts rather than simple changes in their standing biomass. In the low-flow treatments, many benthic insect taxa advanced or delayed their peak abundances relative to the control hydrograph, and the emergent insect assemblages exhibited changes in species composition and emergence timing. Most of the taxa that contributed to community dissimilarity between treatments were those that changed phenology rather than those that were lost altogether (Leathers *et al.* 2024). In other words, the community re-timed itself in response to earlier and more prolonged low-flow periods. Notably, this ecological shift had important consequences for cross-ecosystem linkages: emergent flux pulses of the dominant insect group (midges, Chironomidae) almost doubled in magnitude, benefitting birds that nested nearby (mostly Brewer's Blackbirds) via an unexpected flux of midges early in the season.

In a second experiment in this outdoor channel system, we examined to what extent insect emergence may respond not just to future low flows arising from snow droughts- but from the interaction between these novel physical conditions and novel biological conditions induced by non-native fish (Evangelista *et al.* 2025). Thus, in addition to manipulating low flow timing (current vs. earlier onset), in half of the channel sections we added non-native brown trout (*Salmo trutta*), a widespread invader in cold-water streams globally. We found that low flows and non-native fish presence had largely additive effects, with non-native trout increasing the seasonally aggregated abundance of emerging insects by up to approximately 12%, mainly by increasing the emergence of Chironomidae and small-bodied mayflies and caddisflies (Evangelista *et al.* 2025). These patterns suggest that invasive predators and climate-driven flow changes can jointly, but additively, reshape the magnitude, timing, and size structure of cross-ecosystem fluxes.

Notably, some observed ecological changes may not be evident from the standpoint of numerical abundance or community composition alone. In this vein, by combining stable isotope analysis with gut content data, we measured changes in the isotopic niche space of three abundant predatory taxa (a Perlidae stonefly, a *Rhyacophila* caddisfly, and turbellarian flatworms; Fig. 2). We found that low flows led to reductions in niche areas, consistent with the idea that environmental stress can narrow diet breadth as predators lose access to certain prey or become more specialized (Cowell *et al.* 2025). This work points toward a key mechanism by which snow droughts may erode food-web stability: by changing foraging choices. Indeed, if extended low flows reduce prey diversity or accessibility, predators may rely on a narrower set of resources, which theory and empirical work suggest increases the vulnerability of food webs to further perturbations (Rooney *et al.* 2006).

Fig. 2 Large stonefly nymph (*Doroneuria*) that specializes in cold-water Sierra Nevada streams. Credit: David Herbst.

Taken together, these experiments provide a mechanistic picture of how snow droughts may alter mountain stream food webs. Earlier, extended low flows shift biofilm metabolism toward higher respiration during critical windows, constrain the foraging choices of predators, and alter the phenology and dynamics of benthic insects that ultimately emerge and connect the stream ecosystem with riparian and terrestrial environments. Importantly, many of these changes occur at fine temporal scales (e.g., over days to weeks) and would likely be overlooked if measurements were taken opportunistically or if they were averaged over time (e.g., seasonally aggregated).

In addition to highlighting the importance of high-frequency sampling, our results suggest the need for further investigation into how the multiple dimensions of global change converge in mountain streams. Climate-induced shifts in snowpack and flow regimes can interact with water abstraction, land-use change, and biological change (e.g., via invasions and extinctions), thereby shaping ecological outcomes (Palmer *et al.* 2008; Siirila-Woodburn *et al.* 2021). Extending experiments and long-term observations to systems with stronger human modification, such as large regulated rivers and urban catchments, would allow us to better understand the role that environmental flow management could play in driving river ecosystem restoration outcomes in the future (Palmer & Ruhi 2019, Tonkin *et al.* 2019).

Looking ahead, I see several key questions and opportunities for limnologists interested in climate impacts on freshwater ecosystems under an increasingly extreme water cycle: (1) Will climate “whiplash” (i.e., intensifying extremes) erode the capacity of stream populations to migrate, acclimate, or locally adapt to changing conditions? (2) To what extent will phenological shifts at lower trophic levels (algal production, stream insect growth, and emergence) propagate to riparian predators (e.g., insectivorous birds), and when can we expect climate-induced trophic mismatches or even ‘novel matches’? (3) Is drought changing the nutritional value of cross-ecosystem linkages, for example, by altering the synthesis and transfer of unique fatty acids (e.g., LC-PUFA) from algae to aquatic and riparian consumers? (4) Finally, how can ecological insights from experiments and long-term observations be incorporated into environmental flow and river ecosystem restoration practices that explicitly account for low-to-no snow futures?

Addressing these questions will require continued integration across disciplines and scales, from global hydrologic modelling to fine-scale experiments, such as those described here, and from individual physiology and behavior to food-web structure and whole-ecosystem functioning. As the cryosphere recedes, the seasonal pulse of snowmelt that has long-structured mountain rivers is being rewritten. For regions such as California and many other snow-dependent regions worldwide, sound science will be essential to safeguard freshwater and the integrity of the ecosystems that depend on it.

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References

- Baxter, C.V., Fausch, K.D. and Saunders, W.C., 2005. Tangled webs: reciprocal flows of invertebrate prey link streams and riparian zones. *Freshwater Biology*, 50(2), 201-220.
- Carlson, S.M., Ruhí, A., Bogan, M.T., Hazard, C.W., Ayers, J., Grantham, T.E., Batalla, R.J. and Garcia, C., 2024. Losing flow in free-flowing Mediterranean-climate streams. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 22(5), e2737.

Cowell, A., Leathers, K., de Mendoza, G., Dwyer, G., Herbst, D. and Ruhí, A., 2025. Experimentally induced low flows indicate climate change may shrink trophic niches of mountain-stream predators. *Freshwater Science*, 44(3):330-347.

Evangelista, C., Leathers, K., Buoro, M., Tronel, T., Carlson, S.M. and Ruhí, A., 2025. Prolonged low flows and non-native fish operate additively to alter insect emergence in mountain streams. *Limnology and Oceanography*, doi: 10.1002/lno.70112.

Huning, L.S. and AghaKouchak, A., 2020. Global snow drought hot spots and characteristics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(33), pp.19753-19759.

Kharouba, H.M. and Wolkovich, E.M., 2020. Disconnects between ecological theory and data in phenological mismatch research. *Nature Climate Change*, 10(5), pp.406-415.

Leathers, K., Herbst, D., de Mendoza, G., Doerschlag, G. and Ruhí, A., 2024. Climate change is poised to alter mountain stream ecosystem processes via organismal phenological shifts. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121(14), p.e2310513121.

Leathers, K., Herbst, D., Bogan, M., Jeliazkov, G. and Ruhí, A., 2025. Ecological pathways connecting riverine drought to community change across space and time. *Ecological Monographs*, 95(3), p.e70035.

Mote, P.W., Li, S., Lettenmaier, D.P., Xiao, M. and Engel, R., 2018. Dramatic declines in snowpack in the western US. *Npj Climate and Atmospheric Science*, 1(1), p.2.

Palmer, M. A., C. A. Reidy Liermann, C. Nilsson, M. Flörke, J. Alcamo, P. S. Lake, and N. Bond. 2008. Climate change and the world's river basins: Anticipating management options. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 6: 81–89.

Palmer, M. and Ruhí, A., 2019. Linkages between flow regime, biota, and ecosystem processes: Implications for river restoration. *Science*, 365(6459), p.eaaw2087.

Power, M.E., Chandra, S., Gleick, P. and Dietrich, W.E., 2024. Anticipating responses to climate change and planning for resilience in California's freshwater ecosystems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121(32), p.e2310075121.

Reich, K.D., Berg, N., Walton, D.B., Schwartz, M., Sun, F., Huang, X. and Hall, A., 2018. Climate change in the Sierra Nevada: California's water future. *UCLA Center for Climate Science*.

Rooney, N., McCann, K., Gellner, G. and Moore, J.C., 2006. Structural asymmetry and the stability of diverse food webs. *Nature*, 442(7100), pp.265-269.

Siirila-Woodburn, E.R., Rhoades, A.M., Hatchett, B.J., Huning, L.S., Szinai, J., Tague, C., Nico, P.S., Feldman, D.R., Jones, A.D., Collins, W.D. and Kaatz, L., 2021. A low-to-no snow future and its impacts on water resources in the western United States. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 2(11), 800-819.

Tonkin, J.D., Poff, N.L., Bond, N.R., Horne, A., Merritt, D.M., Reynolds, L.V., Olden, J.D., Ruhí, A. and Lytle, D.A., 2019. Prepare river ecosystems for an uncertain future. *Nature*, 570(7761), pp.301-303.

Hacha river, Florencia, Caquetá, Colombia.
Photo by Estefanía Guerra Montealegre